

SIMILAR AND DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF UZBEKI AND ARABIC LANGUAGE PHONETICS

RAHIMJONOVA ROZIYA ABDURASHID QIZI

SCHOOL 43, NAMANGAN CITY

"OFTOB" IS A MEMBER OF THE ART AND LITERATURE CLUB

Abstract. In this article, the similarities and differences between the Arabic and Uzbek languages, as well as phonetic and sound system aspects, are discussed in particular.

Key words. Phonetics, sound system, comparative linguistics, historical process.

Language refers to a complex system of communication or the ability to learn and use that system. Language is primarily a means of communication. The field that studies language is called linguistics. To determine the number of world languages, it is necessary to distinguish between language and dialect. Nevertheless, the number of languages is considered to be between 6-7 thousand. In a broad sense, the term language refers to a set of specific rules of a communication system.

Arabic is a language belonging to the southern branch of the Semitic language group. It is the official state language of more than 586 countries in the Middle East and North Africa. Arabic is spoken by more than 200 million people (1997). The ancient Arabic language is known through monuments dating back to the 4th-5th centuries BC. It was the basis for the emergence of the classical Arabic language. The lexical and grammatical formation of classical Arabic language began to appear in the oral works of poets of Jahiliyyah (5-7 centuries). As a result of the revelation of the Holy Qur'an, the art of the classical Arabic language became more beautiful and its grammatical norms were perfected.

There are 28 letters in the Arabic alphabet. There are 29 letters in the Uzbek alphabet, 3 of which are combinations of letters. They are: "sh", "ch", "ng". The pronunciation of almost all the letters of the Arabic alphabet is similar to the letters of the Uzbek language. An example of this: б, т, ж, х, дж, д, р, с, ш, ф, к, м, н, в, ы.

The pronunciation of these letters is similar to the letters of the Uzbek language. The difference between the Uzbek language and the Arabic language is that some vowels in the Uzbek language are expressed in Arabic by putting a sign under or above the words. There are 3 character movements in Arabic. They are as follows: damma, fatha, kasra. In Uzbek, damma corresponds to "u", fatha

corresponds to "a", and kasra corresponds to "i".

The most interesting thing is that some words in the Uzbek language are taken from the Arabic language. Let me give an example of this: ктб, клм, дфтр, двля китб, калам, дафтр датв and some other words. When I heard these words, I thought that "Arabs pronounce these words like us." Then I found out that we pronounce it like Arabs.

Arabic is the language of heaven. In Uzbek, words are written from ten to ten. In Arabic, it is written from right to left. Of course, in Arabic, punctuation marks are placed from right to left. In Arabic, words such as Uzbek are not written with capital letters. There are also many Arabic words in the Russian language, such as: algebra, algorithm, giraffe, zenith, syrup, sofa, tariff, chemistry, elikziz and other words. In Arabic, syllables are not moved, so the word can be written so that there is no space left at the end of the line. There are 12,300,000 words in the Arabic language.

Let me tell you some interesting facts about the Uzbek language. The Uzbek language combines three branches of the Turkic languages - Kargul, Kipchak and Ogiz dialects. The Uzbek language is one of the 50 languages of the world. It ranks second among related languages in terms of the number of dialects. Uzbek language and literature are taught in about 70 universities around the world. During the entire history of development, there were three types of writing in the Uzbek language. Until the end of the 20s of the last century, the ethnic group of Uzbeks was based on the Arabic alphabet. With the advent of the Soviet government, the script underwent a number of reforms. Later, the Latin alphabet was used until 1938, and then it was switched to the Cyrillic alphabet. After the Republic of Uzbekistan became an independent country, it returned to the Latin alphabet in 1993.

The Uzbek language that we speak now was formed in the 20th century, and the Fergana dialect, recognized by the people of Uzbekistan, formed its basis. Speaking this dialect, which the majority of the population knows as Sartya, and its speakers are called Sarts. Ethnic sarts did not belong to the Uzbek people, but in the 20s of the last century, the word "sart" was abandoned and the inhabitants of the country began to be called Uzbeks.

Now let's study the history of the Arabic language. Arabic as a language began to take shape after the 6th century. During this period, the special laws of sarf (word structure, morphology) and nakhv (sentence structure, syntax) in the Arabic language were produced by major scientists. Mahmud al-Zamakhshari, who grew up in our country, created major works on the grammar of the Arabic language and called the eras "Al-Inmujaz".

Arab scholars: "If it were not for the famous Khorezm resident Mahmud al-

Zamakhshari, we would have passed without knowing the Arabic language." Because az-Zamakhshari explained Arabic grammar in detail in his works. His works are considered to be the largest works on the grammar of the Arabic language.

In conclusion, it can be said that the phonetics of the Arabic and Uzbek languages are very similar to each other and have many different aspects. Therefore, it is good to study the phonetics of both languages in comparison with each other.

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